

EXPLORING JOB SATISFACTION AMONG ELLIPSO LOGISTICS PVT. LTD. EMPLOYEES IN CHENNAI: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Employee satisfaction, measuring the degree of contentment with one's job and workplace, holds significant implications for business success. A high level of employee morale correlates with increased productivity, reduced absenteeism, and enhanced organizational loyalty. This study aims to assess the job satisfaction level among employees of Ellipso Logistics Pvt. Ltd. in Chennai. Secondary objectives include examining employee perceptions of policies such as leave, insurance, and working hours, evaluating work-life balance, assessing management-employee communication effectiveness, and gauging satisfaction with workplace amenities and infrastructure. The study employs selected multiple-choice questions to gather data.

1.INTRODUCTION

In any business, productivity is extremely crucial. Unhappy workers bring direct issues to their specific company. But if these issues are not sufficiently addressed, they often spread to other companies, sectors, and areas, damaging relationships, earnings, productivity, and ultimately the process of generating wealth for the country. This study is being conducted because increasing job satisfaction is one method to increase work efficiency. The current focus on “Exploring Job Satisfaction among Ellipso Logistics Pvt. Ltd. Employees in Chennai. A Comprehensive Study”

A Logistics Employee is employed by a logistics firm or the logistics division of an organization. They are in charge of assisting with the organization's supply chain operations coordination, planning, execution, and monitoring. They might be responsible for working in the receiving and shipping departments, or they might help the logistics manager with all facets of warehouse

operations. Job Satisfaction is the degree of contentment with one's job is referred to as employee satisfaction. Along with daily tasks, this also takes into account the employees' personal lives and their happiness with team members, managers, and organizational regulations. The combination of positive and negative emotions that employees have towards their employment is known as job satisfaction.

(The International Journal of Indian Psychology ,Volume 11, Issue 2, April- June, 2023,prepared by Ananya , Vimala)¹

Job is one of the important elements of people's life. Their living style and their social lives depend on their jobs. Therefore, it is necessary for every organization to have satisfied workforce. They are not only providing good services but are also providing job opportunities to a large group of people. Keeping in view the contribution of private sector in the society and the significant role of job satisfaction in order to improve the employees' performance, the aim of the present study is to know the job satisfaction of employees and its relationship with the performance level.(Education research article ,volume,2021,**Wasaf Inayat** and Muhammad Jahanzeb Khan, **Published** 05 Aug 2021)²

The employee is an essential element in the process of implementing the enterprises mission and vision, especially in the production sphere. Employees should meet the performance criteria set by the organization to ensure the quantity and quality of their work. To meet organizational standards, employees need a work environment that allows them to work freely without problems that can stop them from reaching their full potential . They also need appropriate superior that will provide them with this environment, but above all, he will motivate them to work in the right way, make them feel satisfied with their work. (CzOTO 2020, volume 2, issue 1, pp. 18-25,Szymon T. Dziuba,Manuela IngaldiMarina, Zhuravskaya.)³

Job satisfaction, Work Environment, Employees organisation is a set-up where people with various capabilities and aptitudes work together toward achieving an identical goal. Organization works smoothly provided some factors are appropriately considered. These factors can be varied, for instance, organizational culture, motivation, effective communication, satisfaction, environment, etc. (The International Journal of Indian Psychology , Volume 11, Issue 1, January-March, 2023 ,Aggarwal, A., Sharma, D., Vohra, P., Sharma, S., & Sharma V.)⁴

The importance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) SMEs in the economy, it is necessary to maintain and sustain the sector's human resource performance. A strand of the literature highlighted that firm-specific factors and the environment impact employee performance. Another strand of the literature highlighted that the performance of an employee could be influenced by cognitive factors, such as individual quality. (**Original research article**, Front. Psychol., 20 June 2022, Volume 13 - 2022)⁵

Job Satisfaction thus is a set of favorable or unfavorable feelings and emotions with which employees view their work. A person with high level of job satisfaction holds positive feelings about the job, while a person who is dissatisfied with his/ her job holds negative feelings about the job.Job satisfaction is an important concern for both the employee as well as the employer as

it has an impact on many organizational behaviors. The employees satisfaction is conducted to provide the information needed to improve various factors like productivity loyalty and job satisfaction. (European Journal of Business and Management www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Online) Vol 3, No.4, 2011 by Neeraj Kumari.)⁶

Employee job satisfaction has a significant impact on an organization's success. It's important to understand how to keep workers by keeping them happy and empowered to produce exceptional results. Employee job satisfaction motivates workers, which helps companies maintain standards and increase productivity. Employment satisfaction is an emotional reaction to one's work environment. As a result, it can only be assumed rather than seen. How well the results meets or exceeds expectations is also a determining factor in job satisfaction. (IJCRT | Volume 9, Issue 4 April 2021 | ISSN: 2320-2882 IJCRT2104110 International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), Ms. Ganga Kalita and Mr. John Paul M)⁷

Job satisfaction has been defined as a "pleasurable or positive emotional state, resulting from the appraisal of one's job experiences". Job satisfaction reflects on overall life quality involving social relationships, family connection and perceived health status, affecting job performances, work absenteeism and job turnover, leading, in some cases, to serious psychological condition such as burnout.(Paolo Montuori, Michele Sorrentino, int J Environ Res Public Health,2022 Oct 31)⁸

The importance and role of logistics in the economic development of the country have been recognized a long time ago. The logistics sector is characterized by a very dynamic market with strong competition and constant changes. Changes at the global, regional and national level directly affect changes in the logistics sector. Recently, labor has been stated as one of the main problems in logistics. In the literature, more emphasis is placed on human resource management in logistics and supply chains. Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering.(University of Belgrade, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia *Logistics 2022*, **Published: 18 July 2022** by Milan Andrejić and Milorad Kilibarda and Vukašin Pajić.)⁹

Success in the freight logistics industry depends, in part, on the quality of service provided by the company. The quality of service provided is to a large extent, determined by employees who form the front line contact with clients. If employees in a freight logistics company are disgruntled with their employers, they typically to pass on their dissatisfaction to the clients. This has adverse consequences on customer satisfaction and loyalty, which in turn, negatively affects profits and overall prosperity of the enterprise. (Advances in Business-Related Scientific Research Conference 2015 in Milan, ABSRC 2015 Milan) December 10-11, 2015, Milan, Italy.)¹⁰

2. SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

- Employee happiness contributes to enhanced performance.
- It acts as a catalyst for employee motivation.
- It fosters staff loyalty towards the organization.
- It inspires employees to exert extra effort to enhance business outcomes.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

Primary Objective:

To conduct a comprehensive study on job satisfaction among employees of Ellipso Logistics Pvt. Ltd. in Chennai.

Secondary Objectives:

- To gauge employees' perceptions of various policies such as leave, insurance, and working hours.
- To assess the work-life balance among employees.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of communication between management and staff.
- To determine the level of satisfaction among staff with regard to the workplace environment and amenities.
- To ascertain the degree of contentment that staff members have with the workspace and its amenities.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Plunkett and Attner (1994) emphasize that unmet needs can frustrate an employee, impacting their behavior until satisfied. Managers can effectively address this by identifying the employee's needs and creating opportunities in the work environment to fulfill them.

Research has extensively explored the relationship between job satisfaction and various work-related behaviors and attitudes, such as job performance, stress, health, life satisfaction, turnover, commitment, and pro-organizational behaviors. However, findings have been inconsistent, possibly due to variations in defining job satisfaction and measuring it (Cranny, Smith, & Stone, 1992).

A path analysis conducted by Cranny, Smith, & Stone (1992) indicates that job satisfaction significantly influences job performance as rated by supervisors, suggesting increased alertness and focused attention. Interestingly, efforts expenditure positively affects

self-rated job performance but inversely relates to supervisor-rated performance. This discrepancy may stem from employees' self-perceptions. Neither self-reported nor supervisor-reported job performance substantially influences job satisfaction, indicating a non-bidirectional relationship.

Plunkett and Attner (1994) further stress that managers can address employees' unmet needs by understanding and facilitating opportunities for satisfaction within the work environment.

Cranny, Smith, & Stone (1992) suggest that the methods used to study performance and satisfaction influence the conclusions about their relationship. They argue that correlational studies suggest a stronger relationship between the two.

Job satisfaction, widely acknowledged as a critical and frequently studied attitude, is challenging to define and measure accurately. According to Cranny, Smith & Stone (1992), it is generally regarded as an affective reaction to a job, resulting from employees comparing actual outcomes with desired ones.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE: 1 SATISFIED WITH THE WORK ENVIRONMENT IN THE ORGANIZATION

PARTICULAR	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Strongly Agree	11	10
Agree	55	50
Neutral	33	30
Disagree	7	6
Strongly Disagree	4	4
Total	110	100

CHART: 1**INTERPRETATION:**

Based on the table provided, it is evident that 50% of the respondents agree that they are satisfied with the work environment in their organization. Additionally, 30% of the respondents either agree or disagree with their satisfaction level regarding the work environment. The majority of respondents express agreement with their satisfaction level in the organization's work environment.

TABLE: 2 BELIEVES JOB IS SECURE

PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Strongly Agree	0	0
Agree	42	38
Neutral	46	42
Disagree	13	12
Strongly Disagree	9	8
Total	110	100

CHART: 2**INTERPRETATION:**

The table 2 indicates that 42% of the respondents either agree or disagree that they believe their job is secure, while 38% of the respondents agree that they believe their job is secure. Overall, it can be observed that the majority of respondents express agreement or disagreement regarding their perception of job security.

TABLE: 3 FEEL SALARY IS FAIR FOR RESPONSIBILITIES

PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Strongly Agree	9	8
Agree	33	30
Neutral	60	55
Disagree	8	7
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Total	110	100

CHART: 3**INTERPRETATION:**

Based on Table 3, it can be interpreted that 55% of the respondents either agree or disagree that they feel their salary is fair for their responsibilities. Additionally, 30% of the respondents agree that they feel their salary is fair for their responsibilities. Overall, the majority of respondents express some level of agreement or disagreement regarding their perception of salary fairness relative to their responsibilities.

TABLE: 4 HAPPY WITH THE WORKING HOURS IN THE ELLIPSO LOGISTICS PVT. LTD.,

PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Strongly Agree	33	30
Agree	55	50
Neutral	11	10
Disagree	7	6
Strongly Disagree	4	4
Total	110	100

CHART: 4**INTERPRETATION:**

According to Table 4, it can be interpreted that 50% of the respondents either agree or strongly agree that they are happy with the working hours at Ellipso Logistics Pvt Ltd. Additionally, 30% of the respondents strongly agree that they are happy with the working hours. Overall, the majority of respondents express agreement or strong agreement regarding their satisfaction with the working hours at Ellipso Logistics Pvt Ltd.

6. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS**ANOVA****ONE-WAY ANOVA CLASSIFICATION****Null hypothesis (H₀):**

There is a significance difference between level of employment and performed well and can count on being promoted.

Alternate hypothesis (H₁):

There is no significance difference between level of employment and performed well and can count on being promoted.

Descriptive

LEVEL OF EMPLOYMENT

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Strongly Agree	9	1.00	.000	.000	1.00	1.00	1	1
Agree	68	1.51	.503	.061	1.39	1.64	1	2
Neutral	33	2.97	.174	.030	2.91	3.03	2	3
Total	110	1.91	.819	.078	1.75	2.06	1	3

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

LEVEL OF EMPLOYMENT

Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
329.552	2	107	.000

LEVEL OF
EMPLOYMENT

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	55.136	2	27.568	164.287	.000
Within Groups	17.955	107	.168		
Total	73.091	109			

Tabulated value = 3.09

Calculated value = 164.287

$$F = F_{cal} > F_{tab} \quad F = 164.287 > 3.09$$

Hence, the null hypothesis [H₁] is accepted.

INFERENCE:

Since the calculated value is greater than the tabulated value, we accept the alternate hypothesis. Therefore, there is a relationship between the level of employment and performance as well as the likelihood of being promoted.

ANALYSIS USING KARL PEARSON'S CORRELATION

Correlation analysis is the statistical tool used to measure the degree to which two variables are linearly related to each other. Correlation measures the degree of association between two variables.

Null hypothesis (H₀):

There is no positive relationship between personal life and work life is balanced and personal problems don't affect work at Ellipso Logistics Pvt Ltd.

Alternate hypothesis (H1):

There is negative relationship between personal life and work life is balanced and personal problems don't affect work at Ellipso Logistics Pvt Ltd.

Correlations

		PERSONAL LIFE AND WORK LIFE IS BALANCED	PERSONAL PROBLEMS DON'T AFFECT WORK AT ELLIPSO LOGISTICS PVT LTD
PERSONAL LIFE AND WORK LIFE IS BALANCED	Pearson Correlation	1	.888**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	110	110
PERSONAL PROBLEMS DON'T AFFECT WORK AT ELLIPSO LOGISTICS PVT LTD	Pearson Correlation	.888**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	110	110

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

$$r = \frac{N\sum XY - \sum X\sum Y}{\sqrt{N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \sqrt{N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

$$rr = .888$$

INFERENCE:

Since the correlation coefficient (r) is positive, it indicates a positive relationship between personal life and work-life balance, suggesting that personal problems do not significantly affect work at Ellipso Logistics Pvt. Ltd.

7. CONCLUSION

While having happy workers is generally beneficial for a company, it's essential to ensure that underperforming employees don't remain solely because they enjoy their jobs. Factors such as respect for workers, frequent employee recognition, competitive benefits and compensation, employee perks, engaging company activities, and positive management practices contribute to employee satisfaction.

The aim of this study was to assess the overall job satisfaction of employees at Ellipso Logistics Pvt Ltd. Through the analysis of employee responses, several recommendations have been proposed to the management of Ellipso Logistics Pvt. Ltd. to enhance overall job satisfaction among Employees.

The purpose of this study is to ascertain how satisfied employees at Ellipso Logistics Pvt Ltd are with their jobs overall. Employee responses have been gathered and examined for this purpose. A few insightful recommendations have been made to Ellipso Logistics Pvt. Ltd's management based on the study's findings in order to raise overall job satisfaction.

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